

Nomenclatural novelties in *Lepisorus* (Polypodiaceae)

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Abstract: A new combination *Lepisorus chinensis* (Mett. ex Kuhn) Deroliya & Sanjeet Kumar and a replacement name *Lepisorus harishchandrii* Deroliya & V. K. Rawat are proposed for *Polypodium chinense* Mett. ex Kuhn and *Tricholepidium venosum* Ching, respectively.

Keywords: Bhutan, China, India, *Neocheiropteris*, New combination, Replacement name

Introduction

The genus *Lepisorus* (J.Sm.) Ching (Polypodiaceae) is represented by about 80 species, distributed mainly in the tropical and subtropical parts of the Old World (Hennipman et al., 1990; Zhao et al., 2020a; POWO, 2025). In the current circumscription the genus *Neocheiropteris* Christ is considered synonymous with *Lepisorus* (J. Sm.) Ching (Testo et al., 2019, Zhao et al., 2020a, b, 2020, Wei and Zhang, 2022, Singh and Rawat, 2024). While working on the family Polypodiaceae for flora of India, we found that *Polypodium chinense* Mett. ex Kuhn and *Tricholepidium venosum* Ching should be transferred to *Lepisorus*. Therefore, a new combination *Lepisorus chinensis* (Mett. ex Kuhn) Deroliya & Sanjeet Kumar and a replacement name *Lepisorus harishchandrii* Deroliya & V.K.Rawat are proposed.

Nomenclature

Lepisorus chinensis (Mett. ex Kuhn) Deroliya & Sanjeet Kumar, **comb. nov.**

≡ *Polypodium chinense* Mett. ex Kuhn, J. Bot. 6: 270. 1868. *Microsorium chinense* (Mett. ex Kuhn) Fraser-Jenk., Taxon. Revis. Indian Subcontinental Pteridophytes: 70. 2008. *Neocheiropteris chinensis* (Mett. ex Kuhn) Fraser-Jenk., Pariyar & Kandel, Ferns Fern-Allies Nepal 1: 39. 2015.

Lectotype: China, Fokein [Fujian], *C.F.M. De Grijis*, herb. *H.F. Hance 6786* (BM 000036770, image!, designated by Fraser-Jenkins *et al.*, 2021); isolectotype: B 200098819 (image!).

Remaining syntypes: China: Canton [Kwangchow or Guangzhou], *C. Gaudichaud* [herb. *F.A.M. Kuhn*] s.n. (B 200098824, image!, P); China: s.l., [1841], *C. Gaudichaud* [herb. *F.A.M. Kuhn*] s.n. (B 200098818a, B 200098822, image!); Chekiang (Zhejiang), Pootoo (Putuo), *R. Fortune 181* (K); Chekiang (Zhejiang), Chusan [Tshu-San, Zhoushan], herb. *C.Fl. Godet* (B 200098818b and K).

= *Polypodium henryi* Christ in Bull. Herb. Boissier 6: 873. 1898. *Microsorium henryi* (Christ) C.M.Kuo in Taiwania 30: 67. 1985. *Neocheiropteris henryi* (Christ) Fraser-Jenk. in New Sp. Syndr. Indian Pteridol.: 179. 1997.

= *Phymatodes takedae* Nakai in Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 43: 2. 1929. *Polypodium takedae* (Nakai) C.Chr. in Index Filic., Suppl. Tert.: 160. 1934. *Microsorium takedae* (Nakai) H.Itô in J. Jap. Bot. 11: 97. 1935.

= *Microsorium excelsum* Ching & S.K.Wu in Fl. Xizang. 1: 327. 1983.

Distribution: Bhutan, China, India (Arunachal Pradesh), Taiwan, Tibet.

Note: Kuhn (1868) described *Polypodium chinense* based on the specimens of then Mettenius herbarium, which were later acquired by B, between 1870 and 1875 and were incorporated in the general herbarium (extant) and the type of F.A.M. Kuhn are housed in B (Stafleu and Cowan, 1979, 1981), therefore, original material (including isolectotype and remaining syntypes) from B is also mentioned above.

Lepisorus harishchandrii Deroliya & V.K.Rawat, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Tricholepidium venosum* Ching, Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 29(1–5): 45. 1978. *Neocheiropteris venosa* (Ching) Fraser-Jenk., Indian J. Forest. 42(4): 314. 2019 (publ. 2020), non *Lepisorus venosus* Ching & S.K.Wu, Acta Bot. Yunnan. 5: 15. 1983.

Holotype: China: N.W. Yunnan, Lung-ling, *K.Chen 764* (PE); Paratype: Taron, 6 Sept. 1938, *T.T. Yu 20149* (PE).

Distribution: Bhutan, China, India (Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Nagaland and Mizoram).

Etymology: The specific epithet is named after author's teacher and former pteridologist of Botanical Survey of India, Late Dr. Harish Chandra Pande (1965–2013).

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